

CERTIFICATE OF APPRECIATION

THIS CERTIFIES THAT
TAFAKKUR MANZILI
JURNALIDA FAOL ISHTIROK ETGANI UCHUN

Gulomova Bibi Mukhlisa

**SIMILAR AND DIFFERENT ASPECTS OF THE CONCEPT OF HAPPINESS IN UZBEK
AND ENGLISH LINGUISTIC CULTURE**

NOMLI MAQOLASI BILAN ISHTIROK ETGANI UCHUN TAQDIRLANADI

2023/IYUL

